

Determinants of Digital Financial Inclusion - A comparative Study of India, Brazil & United Kingdom

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Purpose/Objective

The financial sector of a country largely impacts its economic growth. This depends upon the extent to which it has reached the citizens. The country where all the people are included in its formal financial sector or are part of it, would be on the path of inclusive growth (Kumar, A., & Singh, S. 2021). The term financial inclusion is what helps a country in not only reducing the level of poverty by timely providing adequate and affordable financial services to all, but would also help in achieving sustained inclusive growth. Thus, financial inclusion plays an important role in a country's financial well-being and digital technology further strengthens financial inclusion success. This is sufficed by P2P lending platforms to a greater extent that use technology to streamline the lending process, making it more efficient and transparent. This can help reduce the cost of lending and increase access to credit for borrowers. This study provides an insight on the current status of financial inclusion capturing two dimensions of financial inclusion - usage of financial services by households and access to financial institutions (Gershenson et al, 2021). The study also examined the digitalisation of financial inclusion and the factors affecting the digital financial inclusion. The study is based on the secondary data collected from published reports of RBI, NPCI, World Bank, ACI Worldwide, articles, websites and reports submitted by different committees on digital transactions over different time periods. The objective of the study is to assess the factors affecting digital financial inclusion initiatives in India and evaluate the comparative impact in the United Kingdom and Brazil.

Research Question:

RQ1: What are the factors affecting Digital Financial Inclusion in India, Brazil and United Kingdom

RQ2: Learning from P2P lending of other countries for India to strengthen Digital Financial Inclusion

Methodology:

Financial Inclusion is measured by 'access' and 'usage' of financial services for the economic benefit reflected in the studies conducted in different countries (Aduda & Kalunda, 2012) (Ozili, 2018) (Aziz & Naima, 2021). Digital financial inclusion enables inclusive growth and makes financial services accessible to the poor and helps them in coming out of the cycle of poverty (Pande et al, 2012). Data for the study were collected from World Bank Global Findex Database and IMF Financial Access Survey (FAS). Variables were identified on the two dimensions of financial inclusion -access and usage of financial services (Gershenson et al, 2021) for India, Brazil and the United Kingdom. The selection of these countries was done on

the basis of GDP volume. A set of digital financial inclusion questions related to the usage of financial products were extracted from the database. Per capita income (used as a dependent variable in regression analysis) is used to measure Financial Inclusion. Factors like - Made of Received Digital Payment, owns a debit or Credit card, used a mobile phone or the internet to access a financial institution account, borrowed from bank, have an account, etc. were used as explanatory variables for usage and access of financial services in sample countries (used as independent variable in regression analysis). Data reduction would be done with the help of factor analysis and results will be used for regression analysis.

Expected Outcomes:

The proposed study is expected to provide insights about the factors affecting Digital Financial Inclusion in India, Brazil and the United Kingdom. Further the study may help to understand how in the United Kingdom and Brazil P2P lending is strengthening Digital Financial Inclusion by reducing cost and enhanced access to credit for borrowers. The study's findings will contribute to the literature on P2P lending and financial inclusion and will have implications for policymakers, regulators, and financial institutions in India.

Reference

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